

SALICYLAMIDOXIME AS AN ANALYTICAL REAGENT. PART IV. SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF IRON

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The use of salicylamidoxime as a reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of iron, by making use of the orange-red colour formed by Fe^{III} with the reagent in alkaline solution, is described. The optimum wave-length for measurement of the colour intensity appears to be $400 m\mu$, since the absorption of the coloured complex shows very little change within the range $390-410 m\mu$ and the freshly prepared reagent shows no absorption in this region. The pH of the solution should be within the limit of 8.3 to 10.0 and an excess of the reagent, at least twenty times the molar proportion of iron, is essential. The colour is stable at room temperature in the pH range mentioned and measurements can be carried out within the range of 0° to 30° . Beer's law holds good within the range 0.28 to 14 p.p.m. of iron, and sensitivity is $0.017 cm^{-1}$. The composition (1:3) of the coloured species has been evaluated by Job's method and a probable constitution has been assigned. The effect of diverse ions on the colour intensity has been investigated and the tolerance limits have been determined. This method therefore requires a previous separation of iron from the interfering radicals as in most other cases.

The colorimetric reagents for iron are fairly numerous, but comparatively few are well suited for the determination of traces of this metal. Of the various reagents employed some react with ferrous ions and some with ferric ions. The latter generally have the disadvantage that they cannot be used in the presence of ions like fluoride, phosphate, pyrophosphate, etc., which strongly mask Fe^{III} in acid solution in which the colour reactions have frequently to be carried out. Determinations of Fe^{III} in alkaline solutions, however, can often be carried out even in presence of appreciable quantities of these otherwise interfering ions.

It has already been pointed out in Part I (Rây and Bandyopadhyay, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 21) that ferric ion gives a strongly coloured soluble complex with salicylamidoxime in alkaline solution which is suitable for the detection of traces of iron. An attempt to use the amidoxime as a reagent for the determination of traces of iron seems desirable since reagents which react in alkaline solution have usually some advantage, as already mentioned. As a result of the present investigation it has been found that the amidoxime is quite useful for the colorimetric determination of iron. The optimum wave-length for measurement of the colour intensity appears to be $400 m\mu$, since the absorption of the coloured complex shows very little change in the region $390-410 m\mu$, and the freshly prepared solution of the reagent shows no absorption at this wave-length. The colour intensity of a solution containing Fe^{III} and excess of the amidoxime reaches its maximum at a pH 8.3 and remains constant up to pH 10. An excess of the reagent over twenty times the molar proportion of iron is without effect on the colour intensity, and Beer's law has been found to hold good within the entire range investigated, i.e., 0.28 to 14 p.p.m. of iron. Sensitivity of the present method is $0.017 cm^{-1}$, and as little as 0.057 Fe per c.c. per cu. can be detected with the instrument. The colour is stable at room temperature and the optical density remains unaltered in the range of 20° - 30° , and even at 40° the decrease is less than 2%.

The composition of the coloured complex has been evaluated by Job's method as in the case of the U^{VI} complex, described in Part III (this issue, p. 269). The results indicate the formation of an 1 : 3 complex between the ferric ion and salicylamidoxime. The fact that the colour is highly soluble in water and cannot be extracted by organic solvents indicates its ionic nature (cf. Part III, *loc. cit.*).

The effect of diverse ions on the colour intensity has been fully investigated. Ions like NO_3^- , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , BO_3^{3-} do not interfere even when present in large excess; oxalate, tartrate, SCN^- and F^- interfere when present in sufficient amounts, while most other ions interfere even in low concentrations.

The present method is highly sensitive, but a previous separation of iron from most other cations and anions is necessary before it can be applied to ores, alloys, etc., as in most other cases.

EXPERIMENTAL

The apparatus and solutions of reagents, alkali, diverse ions, buffers, etc., actually used, are the same as those described in Part III (*loc. cit.*).

Ferric Nitrate Solution.—A stock solution of ferric nitrate was prepared from $Fe(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$ (G.R. - E. Merck) and was standardised gravimetrically as the oxide and volumetrically against potassium dichromate as usual. From this stock solution others of required strengths were prepared by requisite dilution with double-distilled water, containing some nitric acid to prevent the hydrolysis of the salt.

Determination of the Optimum Wave-length for Absorption Measurements.—The absorption spectrum of the coloured complex in presence of an excess of salicyl-

FIG. 1
Absorption spectra at 23°.

Curves A and B refer respectively to 0.00025-M- $Fe(NO_3)_3$
+ 0.005 M-sal.-amidoxime (pH 9.74) and 0.005 M-salicylamidoxime,

amidoxime at a p_H of 9.14 and of the reagent of the same concentration and nearly the same p_H as that of the coloured solution are represented in Fig. 1, from which it follows that the optimum region for measurement of the colour intensity is 400 $m\mu$.

Effect of p_H on the Colour Intensity.—The results show that the colour intensity at 400 $m\mu$ reaches its maximum and is independent of H^+ -ion concentration within the range 8.3-10.0 p_H .

Influence of Reagent Concentration on the Colour Intensity.—It is observed that an excess of reagent over twenty times the molar proportion of iron is without effect on the colour intensity. Measurements have been made at p_H 8.8 $\pm$ 0.1 and 400 $m\mu$.

Variation of Optical Density with the Concentration of Iron (Beer's law).—Results of experiments show that Beer's law is obeyed in the entire range of concentrations investigated, namely 0.28 to 14 p.p.m. of iron. The practical range for measurements in 1 cm. cell is, however, 1.4 to 9.5 p.p.m. of iron so that the transmission lies within the optimum range of 80-20% (optical density 0.1-0.7).

Stability of the Colour at Room Temperature.—The colour is stable at room temperature. Thus, a solution 0.002M in Fe^{3+} and 0.002M in salicylamidoxime at a p_H of 8.94, gave exactly the same optical density of 0.409 per cm. at 400 $m\mu$, even after 24 hours of standing at room temperature (25°).

Influence of Temperature.—The colour intensity remains unaltered within the range of 20°-30°; further increase of temperature leads to a slight and gradual decrease in the optical density of the solution as shown below.

TABLE I

$Fe^{3+} = 0.0001 M$. Salicylamidoxime = 0.004 M. $p_H = 8.87$.

Temp.	20°	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°
Optical density per cm., at 400 $m\mu$	0.410	0.410	0.408	0.406	0.403	0.401

Sensitivity.—The smallest amount of iron that can be detected with the instrument is 0.05 γ per c.c. per cm., while the spectrophotometric sensitivity (cf. Sandell, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 2nd Ed., p. 50, Interscience Publishers Inc., 1950) is 0.01 γ cm.⁻² of iron (cf. Part III, *loc. cit.*).

Composition of the Coloured Product.—This has been determined by following Job's method as in the case of the uranium compound (*loc. cit.*). In order to prevent the precipitation of iron in solutions containing lesser amounts of the reagent, it has been found necessary to work in extremely dilute solutions ($[Fe^{3+}] + [R] = 1.6 \times 10^{-6} M$ in actual experiments; R=salicylamidoxime). Since the absorption of pure iron solutions under the experimental conditions was not found to be negligible, the difference in optical density (D_Δ) of the coloured solution and that containing only Fe^{III} of the same concentration as in the coloured solution was plotted against the composition, $[R]/([R] + [Fe^{3+}])$, of the coloured solution to obtain the composition curves represented in Fig. 2 for two different wave-lengths (400 $m\mu$ & 450 $m\mu$). Each of these passes through a maximum at a composition of 0.75, indicating the formation of an 1:3 complex between Fe^{III} and salicylamidoxime.

Influence of Foreign Ions on the Fe^{III}-salicylamidoxime Colour.—The effect of diverse ions has been studied and the tolerance limits have been determined as in case of the colour system produced by U^{VI} (*loc. cit.*). The results are presented in Table II.

TABLE II

Fe²⁺ = 0.0001 M (5.6 p.p.m. Fe). Salicylamidoxime = 0.002 M.

$\mu_n = 8.9 \pm 0.2$. Temp. = 20°-25°.

Ion.	Added as.	Conc. of ion (p.p.m.)	Observed change in optical density.	Tolerance limit (p.p.m.).
NO ₃ ⁻	KNO ₃	12,000	No change	Large excess
Cl ⁻	KCl	10,000	"	"
SO ₄ ²⁻	Na ₂ SO ₄	14,000	"	"
C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	Na ₂ C ₂ O ₄	500	-4%	
		200	-1.2	250
Tartrate	K-Na-tartrate	1,400	-4.5	
		280	-1.3	300
Citrate	Na ₃ -citrate	30	-4	10
		3	Nil	
BO ₃ ³⁻	Na ₂ B ₄ O ₇	5,000	Nil	Large excess
PO ₄ ³⁻	Na ₂ HPO ₄	20	-5%	
		10	-2	6
F ⁻	NaF	200	-1.5	200
SCN ⁻	KSCN	4,400	+4	
		1,200	+2	1,000
CO ₃ ²⁻	Na ₂ CO ₃	6,000	-2.5	
		3,000	-1.2	4,000
MoO ₄ ²⁻	Na ₂ MoO ₄	400	+3	
		200	+1.4	200
WO ₄ ²⁻	Na ₂ WO ₄	500	+3	
		200	+1.3	200
VO ₃ ⁻	NH ₄ VO ₃	4	+2.2	
		2	+1.2	2
UO ₂ ²⁺	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	...	Interferes at all concentrations	0
Cr ₂ O ₇ ²⁻	K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	2	+20%	0
Bi ³⁺	Bi(NO ₃) ₃	2	Turbid	0
Cu ²⁺	CuCl ₂	1	"	0
Ni ²⁺	NiCl ₂	1	"	0
Co ²⁺	CoCl ₂	3	+2.4%	0
Mn ²⁺	MnCl ₂	1.2	+3.8	0
Cr ³⁺	CrCl ₃	2	+10	0
Ce ⁴⁺	Ce(NO ₃) ₄	1	Turbid	0
Th ⁴⁺	Th(NO ₃) ₄	1	"	0
Th ⁴⁺	Th(SO ₄) ₄	1	"	0

FIG. 2

Job's method (25°).

Procedure.—The iron solution should be in the form of nitrate, chloride or sulphate, and all the iron must be in the ferric state. Interfering ions should be removed by suitable methods as commonly used. An aliquot of the solution should be mixed with at least over twenty times the molar proportion of the pure reagent. It is necessary to add the iron solution to a freshly prepared alkaline solution of the reagent and then adjust the p_H to about 9 by adding acid or alkali as required; the solution is now diluted to a definite volume, and its optical density determined at 400 mμ in a cell of suitable thickness to get the transmission within the optimum range for minimum error. The temperature of the solution should be between 20° and 30° and the concentration of iron should lie preferably between 0.7 and 1.4 p.p.m. From the observed optical density, the amount of iron present can be calculated easily, since the system obeys Beer's law.

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